

EFFECT OF CROSS-LINKING CONDITION ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF OSTEONECTIN-COATED HAP/COLLAGEN

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to evaluate the effect of the preparation condition on the mechanical properties of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin and obtain the optimum design guideline of their preparation. We prepared the collagen fibers using the bio-inspired method. Here, 1-ethyl-3-carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) was selected as the cross-linking agent. The osteonectin as the adhesive protein was applied to conduct the coating of the extracted collagen fibers. The HAp crystals were deposited on the surface of the prepared collagen fibers using the biomimetic deposition method. The tensile tests were carried out using the micro-tensile testing device developed by the authors previously. As a result, the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin was maximized under the EDC and osteonectin concentration of 3 [mmol/L] and 0.5 [$\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$], respectively, but was lower than that without the osteonectin prepared under their optimum condition, for the HAp deposition time of 300 [s]. For the HAp deposition time of 50 [s], the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin was maximized under the EDC and osteonectin concentration of 3-5 [mmol/L] and 0.5 [$\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$], respectively. It is notable that the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin prepared under this condition was comparable to or rather higher than that without the osteonectin prepared under their optimum condition. The tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin prepared under the HAp deposition time of 15 [s] was lower than that of 50 [s]. Since it can be considered that the osteonectin would act as the additional bonding factor between the collagen fibers and HAp crystals, it is suggested that the coating of the osteonectin should be carried out to the HAp/collagen composite fibers prepared under the moderately low EDC concentration.

1 INTRODUCTION

The biomaterials presently used for the artificial bone still have the problems, such as the high stiffness generating the stress shielding and the corrosion in the biological environment. The creation of the artificial bone by the microscopic structural design mimicking the microstructures of bone itself might be one of the candidates to solve these problems. The bone tissue has the composite-like microstructures, where the collagen fibers and the surrounding apatite nano-crystals are compounded and hierarchized, exhibiting the excellent mechanical properties. On this view point, the composite materials consisting of the collagen fibers and the apatite crystals have been actively investigated and developed [1-12]. In future, it is desired to reproduce the real bone structures artificially and optimize the mechanical properties of the artificial bone microstructures. Recently, we have been trying to realize the hydroxyapatite (HAp)/collagen composite materials possessing the optimally composed and layered microstructures mimicking the real bone formation process, using a biomimetic bottom-up approach, as shown in Fig. 1. Here, the optimum preparation conditions could be hierarchically determined based on the micro-tensile tests. This approach would enable the creation of the artificial bone cartridges to the bone defects.

Previously, we had evaluated the effects of the synthesis condition [13] and the HAp deposition condition [14] on the mechanical properties of the collagen fibers. Here, HAp were deposited on the surface of the collagen fibers by the biomimetic deposition method, where the collagen fibers are

dipped into the pseudo body fluid alternatively. In addition, we had started to evaluate the effect of the adhesive protein between the collagen fibers and HAp crystals on the mechanical properties of the HAp/collagen composite fibers [15]. Here, we selected the osteonectin as a representative adhesive protein. As a result, the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers prepared under the optimum condition was decreased by the mediation of the osteonectin. This suggests that the individual optimization of the microstructural factors would not necessarily maximize the mechanical properties of the HAp/collagen composite fibers.

Therefore, as a next step, the optimum microstructure of the HAp/collagen composite fibers should be investigated by the parametric study. In this study, we aimed to evaluate the effect of the preparation condition on the mechanical properties of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin and obtain the optimum design guideline of their preparation.

Figure 1: Bottom up design approach for artificial manufacturing of “natural” bone.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Preparation of HAp/collagen composite fibers

In this study, the fish collagen peptides (Tsuji Oil Mill Co. Ltd., origin: scales of freshwater fishes) were used to prepare the collagen fibers. Even though the atelocollagen is widely applied in the medical field, it was not used in this study. This is because the fibrosis of the collagen is hardly arisen if the telopeptides are removed by the pepsin digestion process. The collagen solution of 0.1 [wt%] was prepared using the fish collagen peptides and distilled water. The sodium phosphate buffer of 40 [mmol/L] was prepared to control the pH as 7 using the sodium dihydrogen phosphate (Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd.) and disodium hydrogen phosphate (Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd.). To delay the collagen fibrosis and consequently make it easier to extract the collagen fibers, the sodium chloride (Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd.) solution of 1-2 [mol/L] was prepared. These solutions were precooled at 4 to 10 degree C in a refrigerator for a day. After the precooling, these solutions were mixed with the sodium chloride solution. To generate the cross-linking of the collagen molecules, the solution of the 1-ethyl-3-carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) (Dojindo Molecular Technologies, Inc.) of 1-5 [mmol/L] was added. This mixture was maintained at 25 degree C for 6 days using a water bath.

In this study, the osteonectin (SPARC/BM-40, originated from human being, recombinant) (Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd.) was selected as the adhesive protein. First, the osteonectin of 50 [μ g] and sterilized distilled water of 50 [μ L] were mixed. This solution was applied to the extracted collagen fibers using the micro bullets to conduct the coating of the collagen fibers.

In this study, the HAp deposition on the collagen fibers was carried out using the alternate immersion method [16]. The tris-HCl buffer was prepared by mixing the tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane hydrochloride (Sigma-Aldrich Co. LLC.), tris base (Sigma-Aldrich Co. LLC.) and distilled water. The “Ca solution” was prepared by mixing the tris-HCl buffer and calcium chloride (Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd.) of 200 [mmol]. The “P solution” was prepared by mixing the disodium hydrogen phosphate (Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd.) of 120 [mmol] and distilled water. The collagen fibers were alternatively dipped into the “Ca solution” and “P solution” as the pseudo body fluids, in order to deposit the HAp crystals. The dipping time and

temperature was 15-300 [s] and 37 [degree C], respectively.

2.2 Micro-mechanical testing procedure

The micro-tensile test was carried out using the system developed by the authors previously [13]. As shown in Fig. 2, this testing device utilizes the deflection of the cantilever beam to detect the tensile load applied to the HAp/collagen fibers. Here, the effect of the large-scale deformation was ignored. The HAp/collagen composite fiber was adhered to one end of a glass fiber (WFA230 100BS6, $\phi = 8.50$ [μm]) (Nitto Boseki Co., Ltd.) and a boron fiber (KPSI500, $\phi = 100$ [μm]) (AVCO), in turn, using the small amount of cyanoacrylate adhesive (Toagosei Co. Ltd.). The boron fiber was fixed to the spindle of the micrometer. Here, the boron fiber was arranged parallel to the spindle axis. Then, another end of the glass fiber was fixed on the acrylic basis. Here, the glass fiber was arranged perpendicularly to the boron fiber. The acrylic plate used as the basis of this micro-tensile testing system was treated with the release agent in advance, in order to prevent the adhesion with adhesive used for the bonding between the glass fiber and the HAp/collagen composite fiber and also decrease the friction force. During the micro-tensile tests, the acrylic plate was moderately moistened by adding distilled water using a syringe, in order to prevent the drying of the HAp/collagen composite fibers.

The deflection applied to the glass fiber by pulling the boron fiber using the micrometer was observed using a digital microscope (VHX-500, KEYENCE Corporation) with a zoom lens (VHZ-100, KEYENCE Corporation, 100-1000 times). The tensile strength was calculated using the deflection of the glass fiber at the breakage of the HAp/collagen composite fibers, by assuming the deflection of a cantilever beam and the perfect circular cross section.

Figure 2: Schematic drawing for micro-tensile test.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows the measured tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin, prepared under the HAp deposition time of 300 [s]. The error bars indicate the standard deviation. The dotted line in Fig. 3 indicates the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers without the osteonectin, prepared under the EDC concentration of 5 [mmol/mol] and the HAp deposition time of 300 [s]. It is known that this condition could maximize the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers without the osteonectin [14]. In the case of the EDC concentration of 1 [mmol/L], the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin was increased with the increase in the osteonectin concentration. On the other hand, the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin was decreased with the increase in the osteonectin concentration, in the case of the EDC concentration of 3 and 5 [mmol/L]. For the HAp deposition time of 300 [s], the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin was maximized under the EDC and osteonectin concentration of 3 [mmol/L] and 0.5 [$\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$], respectively, but was lower than that without the osteonectin prepared under their optimum condition.

Figure 4 shows the measured tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin, prepared under the HAp deposition time of 50 [s]. The error bars indicate the standard

deviation. The dotted line in Fig. 4 indicates the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers without the osteonectin, prepared under the EDC concentration of 5 [mmol/mol] and the HAp deposition time of 300 [s]. The tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin was increased and then decreased with the increase in the osteonectin concentration. It is notable that the preparation conditions, where the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin is comparable to or rather higher than that without the osteonectin prepared under their optimum condition, are existing in Fig. 4. For the HAp deposition time of 50 [s], the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin was maximized under the EDC and osteonectin concentration of 3-5 [mmol/L] and 0.5 [$\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$], respectively.

Figure 5 shows the measured tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin, prepared under the HAp deposition time of 15 [s]. The error bars indicate the standard deviation. The dotted line in Fig. 5 indicates the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers without the osteonectin, prepared under the EDC concentration of 5 [mmol/mol] and the HAp deposition time of 300 [s]. The tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin was increased and then decreased with the increase in the osteonectin concentration. Totally, the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin prepared under the HAp deposition time of 15 [s] was lower than that of 50 [s].

Figure 3: Tensile strength of HAp/collagen with osteonectin after HAp deposition for 300 [s].

Figure 4: Tensile strength of HAp/collagen with osteonectin after HAp deposition for 50 [s].

Figure 5: Tensile strength of HAp/collagen with osteonectin after HAp deposition for 15 [s].

Thus, the existence of the osteonectin decreased the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers prepared under their optimum condition without the osteonectin. In addition, the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin was increased and then decreased with the increase in the EDC concentration, the osteonectin concentration and the HAp deposition time. It is known that the osteonectin used as the adhesion protein in this study has the high affinity to the collagen fibers and the HAp crystals [17]. Thus, it can be considered that the osteonectin would act as the additional bonding factor between the collagen fibers and HAp crystals. In this case, it can be expected that the coating of the osteonectin to the HAp/collagen composite fibers prepared under the optimum condition induces the excessive bonding between the collagen fibers and the HAp crystals, as shown in Fig. 6 schematically. This suggests that the coating of the osteonectin should be carried out to the HAp/collagen composite fibers prepared under the moderately low EDC concentration.

Figure 6: Schematic drawing of relation between tensile strength of HAp/collagen composite fibers and crosslinking condition.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to evaluate the effect of the preparation condition on the mechanical properties of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin and obtain the optimum design guideline of their preparation. The obtained results can be summarized as follows.

1. For the HAp deposition time of 300 [s], the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite

fibers with the osteonectin was maximized under the EDC and osteonectin concentration of 3 [mmol/L] and 0.5 [$\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$], respectively, but was lower than that without the osteonectin prepared under their optimum condition.

2. For the HAp deposition time of 50 [s], the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin was maximized under the EDC and osteonectin concentration of 3-5 [mmol/L] and 0.5 [$\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$], respectively. It is notable that the tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin prepared under this condition was comparable to or rather higher than that without the osteonectin prepared under their optimum condition.

3. The tensile strength of the HAp/collagen composite fibers with the osteonectin prepared under the HAp deposition time of 15 [s] was lower than that of 50 [s].

4. Since it can be considered that the osteonectin would act as the additional bonding factor between the collagen fibers and HAp crystals, it is suggested that the coating of the osteonectin should be carried out to the HAp/collagen composite fibers prepared under the moderately low EDC concentration.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Kikuchi, T. Ikoma, S. Itoh, H.N. Matsumoto, Y. Koyama, K. Takakuda, K. Shinomiya and J. Tanaka, Biomimetic synthesis of bone-like nanocomposites using the self-organization mechanism of hydroxyapatite and collagen, *Composites Science and Technology*, **64**, 2004, pp. 819-825 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2003.09.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2003.09.002)).
- [2] W.B. Tien, M.T. Chen and P.C. Yao, Effects of pH and temperature on microstructure and morphology of hydroxyapatite/collagen composites synthesized in vitro, *Materials Science and Engineering Part C*, **32**, 2012, pp. 2096-2102 (doi: [10.1016/j.msec.2012.05.046](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2012.05.046)).
- [3] J. Wang and C. Liu, Biomimetic Collagen/Hydroxyapatite Composite Scaffolds: Fabrication and Characterizations, *Journal of Bionic Engineering*, **11**, 2014, pp. 600-609 (doi: [10.1016/S1672-6529\(14\)60071-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1672-6529(14)60071-8)).
- [4] P. Sasmal and H. Begam, Extraction of Type-I Collagen from Sea Fish and Synthesis of Hap/Collagen Composite, *Procedia Materials Science*, **5**, 2014, pp. 1136-1140 (doi: [10.1016/j.mspro.2014.07.408](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mspro.2014.07.408)).
- [5] G.C.M. Ruiz, M.A.E. Cruz, A.N. Faria, D.C.Z. Zancanela, P. Ciancaglini and A.P. Ramos, Biomimetic collagen/phospholipid coatings improve formation of hydroxyapatite nanoparticles on titanium, *Materials Science and Engineering Part C*, **77**, 2017, pp. 102-110 (doi: [10.1016/j.msec.2017.03.204](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2017.03.204). Epub 2017 Mar 24.).
- [6] T.W. Sun, Y.J. Zhu, F. Chen, F.F. Chen, Y.Y. Jiang, Y.G. Zhang and J. Wu, Ultralong hydroxyapatite nanowires/collagen scaffolds with hierarchical porous structure, enhanced mechanical properties and excellent cellular attachment, *Ceramics International*, **43**, 2017, pp. 15747-15754 (doi: [10.1016/j.ceramint.2017.08.137](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2017.08.137)).
- [7] W. Feng, S. Feng, K. Tang, X. He, A. Jing and G. Liang, A novel composite of collagen-hydroxyapatite/kappa-carrageenan, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, **693**, 2017, pp. 482-489 (doi: [10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.09.234](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2016.09.234)).
- [8] R.X. Sun, Y. Lv, Y.R. Niu, X.H. Zhao, D.S. Cao, J. Tang, X.C. Sun and K.Z. Chen, Physicochemical and biological properties of bovine-derived porous hydroxyapatite/collagen composite and its hydroxyapatite powders, *Ceramics International*, **43**, 2017, pp. 16792-16798 (doi: [10.1016/j.ceramint.2017.09.075](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2017.09.075)).
- [9] H. Begam, S.K. Nandi, A. Chanda and B. Kundu, Effect of bone morphogenetic protein on Zn-HAp and Zn-HAp/collagen composite: A systematic in vivo study, *Research in Veterinary Science*, **115**, 2017, pp. 1-9 (doi: [10.1016/j.rvsc.2017.01.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rvsc.2017.01.012)).

- [10] S. Selvaraju, S. Ramalingam and J.R. Rao, Inorganic apatite nanomaterial: Modified surface phenomena and its role in developing collagen based polymeric bio-composite (Coll-PLGA/HAp) for biological applications, *Colloids and Surfaces Part B: Biointerfaces*, **172**, 2018, pp. 734-742 (doi: [10.1016/j.colsurfb.2018.09.038](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfb.2018.09.038)).
- [11] L. Shen, H. Bu, H. Yang, W. Liu and G. Li, Investigation on the behavior of collagen self-assembly in vitro via adding sodium silicate, *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, **115**, 2018, pp. 635-642 (doi: [10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2018.04.074](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2018.04.074)).
- [12] J. Kozłowska, A. Jundzill, A. Bajek, M. Bodnar, A. Marszałek, H. Witmanowski and A. Sionkowska, Preliminary in vitro and in vivo assessment of modified collagen/hydroxyapatite composite, *Materials Letters*, **221**, 2018, pp. 74-76 (doi: [10.1016/j.matlet.2018.03.122](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2018.03.122)).
- [13] M. Tanaka, M. Shimada, M. Nigorikawa and I. Kimpara, Investigation of optimum synthesis condition of collagen fibers by means of micro-tensile test, *Materials System*, **33**, (2015), pp. 29-35, in Japanese.
- [14] M. Tanaka, A. Kiyoshima, Y. Hasegawa and I. Kimpara, Influence of Alternate Dipping Condition on Tensile Strength of HAp/collagen Composite Fibers, *Materials System*, **36**, (2019), pp. 25-29.
- [15] M. Tanaka, A. Kiyoshima, Y. Hasegawa I. and Kimpara Effect of preparation condition on tensile strength of HAp-deposited collagen fibers, *Proceedings of the 18th European Conference on Composite Materials, Athens, Greece, June 24-28, 2018*, USB, 2018.
- [16] T. Taguchi, A. Kishida and M. Akashi, Fabrication of polymer-apatite composites by using a novel alternate soaking process, *Kobunshi Ronbunshu*, **57**, 2000, pp. 324-335, in Japanese (doi: [10.1295/koron.57.324](https://doi.org/10.1295/koron.57.324)).
- [17] S. Sasaki, Non-collagenous proteins in bone: Osteocalcin and osteonectin, *Japanese Journal of Oral Biology*, **25**, 1993, pp. 847-856, in Japanese (doi: [10.2330/joralbiosci1965.25.847](https://doi.org/10.2330/joralbiosci1965.25.847)).